

THE ACTION OF CHLORINE ON THE HYDROXIDES OF LITHIUM AND POTASSIUM IN THE PRESENCE OF IODINE. PART I

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By passing a brisk current of chlorine through a boiling solution of iodine in lithium hydroxide and potassium hydroxide, dihydrated lithium diparaperiodate, $\text{Li}_8\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $4\text{Li}_2\text{O}, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and potassium metaperiodate, KIO_4 were obtained respectively.

Ammermuller and Manus (*Ann. Physik*, 1833, **28**, 514) prepared disodium paraperiodate, $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$, by passing chlorine into a solution of equal parts of sodium hydroxide and iodate. Wells (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1901, **26**, 278) prepared the same salt by passing a brisk current of chlorine into a boiling solution of sodium hydroxide in the presence of finely powdered iodine. This result was confirmed by Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1091). We have tried this method of obtaining a periodate in the case of lithium and potassium which have been found to yield dihydrated lithium diparaperiodate, $\text{Li}_8\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $4\text{Li}_2\text{O}, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and potassium metaperiodate, KIO_4 respectively.

Analyses of these salts with respect to the alkali metal as sulphate and iodine and available oxygen by the method of Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1085, 1087), have been presented below.

Lithium Salt.

Sample.	Lithium	Iodine.	Available oxygen.
1	10.990%	48.525%	21.165%
2	10.619	48.244	21.379
3	11.00	48.767	21.015

These values show that the lithium salt obtained is a dihydrated lithium diparaperiodate, $\text{Li}_8\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $4\text{Li}_2\text{O}, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The calculated lithium and iodine values are 10.727 and 48.716% respectively. The available oxygen according to the decomposition

is 21.455%.

Potassium Salt.

Sample A was prepared by passing chlorine through a boiling solution of iodine in potassium hydroxide.

Sample B was obtained on cooling the supernatant solution from the above.

Sample A.	K.	I.	Available oxygen.	Sample B.	K.	I.	Available oxygen.
1	16.735%	55.312%	28.030%	1	16.708%	55.267%	27.787%
2	17.141	55.513	28.236	2	17.043	55.398	27.857
3	16.637	55.212	27.787	3	16.759	55.273	27.500

These values agree with potassium metaperiodate, KIO_4 , the calculated values of potassium and iodine being 16.957 and 55.217% respectively. The available oxygen according to the decomposition

is 27.826%.

Ihre (*Ber.*, 1870, 3, 316) also obtained the same salt by the oxidising action of chlorine on a hot solution containing potassium iodate and an excess of potassium hydroxide.

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